

Terpenoids and Related Compounds. Part—XXVI¹. Molecular Rearrangements of 3 α ,4 α - Epoxyfriedoolean-7-one

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Dry hydrogen chloride in chloroform converted 3 α ,4 α -epoxyfriedoolean-7-one (VIII) into putranjivadiolone (X). The cation of borontrifluoride etherate in benzene furnished (X) and 7-ketoglut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (XII), while that of aqueous perchloric acid on the epoxide furnished 7-ketofriedooleana-3 β ,4 α -diol (XV). When the enol (XII) was oxidised with Jones' reagent glut-5(10)-en-3,7-dione (XIV) was obtained.

THE stereochemistry of opening of the epoxide ring, which is dependent on the nature of the reagent, the functional groups in the neighbourhood of the three membered ring and the reaction condition, has been elaborately studied. An extensive progress in kinetics and reaction mechanism has been made due to the stereospecific nature of formation and opening of the epoxide ring. Berti *et al*² have studied the opening of the epoxide ring with various reagents. A number of interesting cases of epoxide ring opening followed by molecular rearrangements have been reported³⁻⁶ in recent years.

By the action of gaseous boron trifluoride or stannic chloride on friedoolean-3 α ,4 α -epoxide (I) ApSimon *et al*⁷ isolated only glut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (II). We previously showed⁸ that the same epoxide (I) on treatment with borontrifluoride etherate in benzene gave a complex mixture consisting of glut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (II), 18 α -olean-12-en-3 α -ol (III), olean-12-en-3 α -ol (IV), olean-13(18)-en-3 α -ol (V) along with the hydrocarbon (VI). Further the action of aqueous perchloric acid on the epoxide (I) furnished friedooleana-3 β ,4 α -diol (VII).

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I. R¹=R²=H
VIII. $\begin{matrix} R^1 \\ R^2 \end{matrix} > =O$

II. R¹=R²=R³=H
XII. $\begin{matrix} R^1 \\ R^2 \end{matrix} > =O, R^3=H$
XIII. $\begin{matrix} R^1 \\ R^2 \end{matrix} > =O, R^3=Ac$

III. $\Delta^{12}, 18\alpha H$
IV. $\Delta^{12}, 18\beta H$
V. $\Delta^{13(18)}$

VI.

VII. R¹=R²=R³=H
XV. $\begin{matrix} R^1 \\ R^2 \end{matrix} > =O, R^3=H$
XVI. $\begin{matrix} R^1 \\ R^2 \end{matrix} > =O, R^3=Ac$

IX.

The present paper deals with the effect of a 7-keto function on such epoxide rearrangement. We have shown before⁹ that the presence of a 7-keto function seriously affected the course of molecular rearrangement of friedoolean-3-ene. For this purpose 3 α , 4 α -epoxyfriedoolean-7-one (VIII) was chosen as the model compound. Friedoolean-3-en-7-one (IX)⁹ was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid to yield mainly the 3 α -epoxide (VIII), m.p. 260-262°, [α]_D+37.93°, M⁺ 440. The PMR spectra showed a triplet (1H) at δ 2.92 due to the β proton as expected⁷. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern (see experimental) was as expected for friedooleananes^{10,11}.

Thus, the presence of a 7-keto function restricts the rearrangement to glutane derivatives and no further rearrangement takes place. In the latter case methyl shift from C-5 takes place in preference to the hydride shift from C-3 at the time of the epoxide ring opening to furnish the alcohol (XII).

On oxidation with Jones' chromic acid reagent¹² the alcohol (XII) furnished glut-5(10)-en-3,7-dione (XIV), m.p. 283-286° which showed IR bands at 1700 (ketones) and 950 cm⁻¹ (tetrasubstituted double bond).

By the action of dry hydrogen chloride in chloroform on the epoxide (VIII), a crystalline compound identified (mixed m.p. and IR) as putranjivadione (X) was obtained. It may be mentioned that the isolation of the dione (X) from the bark of *Putranjiva roxburghii* and its structure determination have previously been described by us^{1,2}. Thus, the formation of the dione (X) proceeded *via* the protonated species (XI) where hydride shift from C-3 rather than methyl shift from C-5 had been preferred with the concomitant ring opening and final equilibration through the enol.

Treatment of the epoxide (VIII) with borontrifluoride etherate in anhydrous benzene for 30 min gave a mixture which could be resolved by chromatography over a column of alumina into two components. The less polar compound was identified (mixed m.p. and IR) as putranjivadione (X). The more polar component, m.p. 305-306°, [α]_D-50.63° was shown to be 7-keto-glut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (XII). In the IR it showed bands at 3520 (hydroxyl) and 1690 cm⁻¹ (β -unsaturated ketone). The absence of any olefinic proton signal in PMR indicated the double bond to be tetrasubstituted. On acetylation, the alcohol (XII) furnished the corresponding acetate (XIII), m.p. 242-246°, [α]_D-68.23° which showed IR bands at 1715 (acetate and ketone), 1240 (acetate) and 945 cm⁻¹ (tetrasubstituted double bond). The PMR spectrum showed an ill defined multiplet (1H) around δ 4.75 which was attributed to the axial proton at C-3 bearing the acetoxy group. There was no signal for any olefinic proton. A singlet (3H) at δ 2.04 was due to the acetoxy methyl group at C-3.

Finally, the epoxide (VIII) was treated with aqueous perchloric acid in tetrahydrofuran to yield mainly a single product that was shown to be 7-ketofriedooleana-3 β , 4 α -diol (XV), m.p. 247-250°, [α]_D+16.86°. On acetylation the diol (XV) gave a monoacetate (XVI), m.p. 278-280°, [α]_D+62.22° which showed IR bands at 3450 (hydroxyl), 1705 (acetate and ketone) and 1245 cm⁻¹ (acetate). The β -orientation of the acetoxy group at C-3 was demonstrated by the PMR spectrum that showed a triplet (1H) centered around δ 4.74 characteristic of an equatorial proton. The acetoxy methyl protons appeared as a singlet (3H) at δ 2.0. Thus in the reaction of the epoxide (VIII) with aqueous perchloric acid nucleophilic attack by water on the protonated epoxide (XI) led to *anti*Markownikoff opening of the epoxide ring to produce the diol (XV).

Experimental

All m.p.s are uncorrected. The pet ether used had b.p. 60-80°. The rotations were taken in chloroform. All the compounds were crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and methanol.

Friedoolean-3-en-7-one (IX) was prepared following the method described by us earlier⁹.

3 α , 4 α -Epoxyfriedoolean-7-one (VIII): A solution of the enone (IX, 0.94 g), *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.69 g) in chloroform (86 ml) was allowed to stand at 0° for 6.5 hr with occasional swirling when TLC indicated the complete consumption of the starting material. Usual work up furnished a semisolid mass

which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (60 g). Elution with a mixture of pet ether and benzene (1:1) yielded a solid which on crystallisation gave the pure epoxide (VIII), m.p. 260–262°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 37.93^\circ$. (Found: C, 82.00; H, 10.95. $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$ requires: C, 81.76; H, 10.98%) *m/e* 440 (M^+), 425, 422, 407, 316, 301, 288, 261, 207, 205, 189 (100%), 123, 121, 109, 97, 95 and 93.

Action of Hydrogen Chloride on the Epoxide (VIII). Putranjivadiolone (X): Dry HCl gas was passed through a solution of the epoxide (VIII, 0.05 g) in chloroform (25 ml) at room temp. for 3 hr. Usual work up furnished a solid (0.04 g) which on crystallisation yielded putranjivadiolone (X), m.p. 276–280° identical (mixed m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic sample^{1,2}.

Action of Borontrifluoride Etherate on the Epoxide (VIII): A solution of the epoxide (VIII, 0.4 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was treated with freshly distilled borontrifluoride etherate (0.4 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. at room temp. Usual work up furnished a crude solid mixture which was chromatographed over a column of alumina (40 g; deactivated with 1 ml of 10% AcOH).

Putranjivadiolone (X): Elution of the above column with a mixture of pet ether and benzene (1:9) gave a crude solid (0.025 g), m.p. 270–274° which on crystallisation furnished putranjivadiolone (X), m.p. 278–280° identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample^{1,2}.

7-Ketoglut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (XII): Elution of the above column with benzene furnished a solid (0.3 g) which on crystallisation yielded 7-ketoglut-5(10)-en-3 α -ol (XII), m.p. 305–306°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 50.63^\circ$. (Found: C, 81.49; H, 10.60. $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$ requires: C, 81.76; H, 10.98%). *m/e* 440 (M^+), 422, 407, 287, 207, 205, 201, 189 (100%), 123, 121, 109, 107, 95 and 93.

7-Ketoglut-5(10)-en-3 α -yl acetate (XIII): The above alcohol (XII, 0.125 g) was acetylated in the usual manner with Ac_2O (1.2 ml) and pyridine (1.2 ml) and the crude acetate on crystallisation furnished the acetate (XIII), m.p. 242–246°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 68.23^\circ$. *UV* λ_{max} 240 nm (ϵ 800) due to the β,γ -unsaturated ketone.

Oxidation of the Alcohol (XII) with Jones' Reagent Glut-5(10)-en-3,7-dione (XIV): A cold solution of the alcohol (XII, 0.13 g) in acetone (300 ml) was treated with Jones' chromic acid reagent¹⁸. After usual work up the crude product (0.13 g) was crystallised to furnish glut-5(10)-en-3,7-dione (XIV), m.p. 283–286°. (Found: C, 81.68; H, 10.65. $C_{30}H_{46}O_2$ requires C, 82.13; H, 10.57%).

Action of Aqueous Perchloric Acid on the Epoxide (VIII): 7-Ketofriedooleana-3 β ,4 α -diol (XV): A solution of the epoxide (VIII, 0.125 g) in THF (6.6 ml) was treated with aq. perchloric acid (3N, 0.9 ml) and the solution was stirred for 8 hr at room temp. Usual work up furnished a solid (0.122 g) which was chromatographed on a column of silica gel (12 g). Elution with a mixture of benzene and EtOAc (4:1) yielded a solid (0.102 g) which on crystallisation gave the pure diol (XV), m.p. 247–250°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 16.86^\circ$. (Found: C, 78.70; H, 11.17. $C_{30}H_{50}O_3$ requires: C, 78.55; H, 10.99%).

3 β -Acetoxy, 4 α -Hydroxyfriedoolean-7-one (XVI): The above diol (XV, 0.13 g) was acetylated in the usual manner with Ac_2O (1.3 ml) and pyridine (1.3 ml) to furnish a product which on crystallisation yielded the monoacetate (XVI), m.p. 278–280°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 62.22^\circ$. (Found: C, 76.82; H, 10.69. $C_{32}H_{52}O_4$ requires: C, 76.75; H, 10.47%).

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